

Expression of key immune genes in polarized porcine monocyte-derived macrophage subsets

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ABSTRACT

Swine are considered one of the most relevant large animal biomedical models since they share many immunological similarities with humans. Despite that, macrophage polarization has not comprehensively investigated in pigs. In this study, porcine monocyte-derived macrophages (moMΦ) were untreated or stimulated with IFN- γ + LPS (classical activation), or by different M2 polarizing stimuli: IL-4, IL-10, TGF- β , or dexamethasone. Expression of key cytokine genes (*IL1B2*, *IL33*, *IL19*, *IL22*, *IL26*, *CCL17*, *CCL24*, *IFNA*, *IFNB*) in macrophage subsets were investigated over time. Expression of the genes encoding the two main enzymes of the arginine pathway (*ARG1*, *NOS2*), and molecules related to alternative macrophage polarization in human and mice (*MMP9*, *MRC1*, *FIZZ1*, *VEGFA*) were also assessed. Stimulation with IFN- γ + LPS triggered up-regulation of *IL1B2*, *IFNB*, *NOS2*, whereas IL-4 triggered up-regulation of *CCL17*, *CCL24*, *CXCR2*, and *ARG1* expression. *IL19* and *IL22* expression was enhanced by stimulation with IFN- γ + LPS or TGF- β , but not IL-4, IL-10, or dexamethasone. Our data highlighted some peculiarities in swine, such as induced expression of *IL33* after stimulation with IFN- γ + LPS, and no up-regulation of *FIZZ1*, *VEGFA* or *MMP9* after exposure to any of the M2 polarizing stimuli. A better understanding of porcine macrophage polarization could benefit translational studies using this large animal model.

1. Introduction

Pigs are attracting increasing attention as a close-to-human model, due to anatomical and physiological similarities (Swindle, 2012). Pigs have been used in the preclinical evaluation of candidate vaccines and therapeutics (Graham et al., 2020; McNee et al., 2020), as well in pre-clinical toxicological testing (Swindle, 2012). These animals are valuable in terms of bridging the gap between laboratory and clinical oncology (Flisikowska et al., 2016), as well as between pre-clinical and clinical studies on nanomaterials (Szebeni et al., 2012, 2020).

There are high similarities between pigs and humans in the anatomy and functions of the immune system (Pabst et al., 2020), however the knowledge on the pig immune system presents several gaps. For example, porcine macrophage polarization has not been characterized in detail. Macrophages are cells of the innate immune system, involved in an array of functions, spanning tissue homeostasis, wound healing, and defense against infective and not infective stressors (Gordon, 2003). Macrophages present extraordinary plasticity, being able to rapidly modify their phenotype and function in response to external stimuli (Hume, 2015). The two opposite extremes of the activation spectrum are

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represented by classically activated macrophages (M1) and alternatively activated macrophages (M2). M1 macrophages are distinguished by enhanced microbicidal or tumoricidal activities, whereas M2 macrophages predominantly mediate wound repair and immunosuppression (Mosser, 2003). M1 macrophages can be generated *in vitro* by exposure to IFN- γ + TNF or its inducer, such as LPS, whereas stimulation with IL-4 or IL-13 can give rise to M2 macrophages (Mosser, 2003). This simplistic model was later refined and three M2 subsets were described: M2a (generated *in vitro* by exposure to IL-4 or IL-13), M2b (generated *in vitro* with immune complexes with IL-1 β or LPS), and M2c (generated *in vitro* by exposure to IL-10, TGF- β or glucocorticoids) (Martinez, 2009). More recently, another M2 subset, termed M2d was described, which was induced by Toll-like receptor (TLR)/adenosine A2A receptor-dependent activation (Griener et al., 2009). M2d are characterized by angiogenic properties and express high levels of both IL-10 and VEGF (Ferrante and Leibovich, 2012). However, in diverse species, including humans and pigs, exposure of macrophages to diverse stimuli can lead to distinct phenotypes. Consequently, a nomenclature based on the activator(s) used, such as M(IL-4), M(IFN- γ + LPS), M(IL-10), M(TGF- β), M(dexamethasone), has been suggested (Murray et al., 2014; Franzoni et al., 2023).

We and others described that porcine macrophage response to external stimuli, such as LPS, resemble those of human macrophages (Franzoni et al., 2023; Fairbairn et al., 2011; Kapentanovic et al., 2012; Kapentanovic et al., 2013). Porcine M(IFN- γ + LPS) possess a phenotype comparable to human and murine cells, with enhanced expression of activation markers and induction/release of proinflammatory cytokines (Franzoni et al., 2023; Singleton et al., 2016; Franzoni et al., 2017). ‘Alternative’ activation of porcine macrophages has been less well studied. Stimulation of porcine macrophages with immunosuppressive cytokines such as IL-10 or TGF- β was not associated with enhanced expression and release of IL-10 (Franzoni et al., 2023; Carta et al., 2021), which is regarded as a hallmark of alternative activation in humans and mice (Shapouri-Moghaddam et al., 2018).

We recently studied porcine macrophage polarization by analyzing gene expression in monocyte-derived macrophages (moM Φ) stimulated with IFN- γ + LPS (classical activation), or by different M2 polarizing stimuli i.e., IL-4, IL-10, TGF- β , or dexamethasone (Franzoni et al., 2023). We identified interesting singularities of pigs (Franzoni et al., 2023), so in this study we aimed to better investigate the phenotype of these six macrophage subsets (moM Φ , moM(IFN- γ + LPS), moM(IL-4), moM(IL-10), moM(TGF- β), moM(dexamethasone). Expression of cytokines, chemokines, and other genes regarded as hallmarks of alternative polarization in human and mice were assessed, to identify potential peculiarities of this species and aid the interpretation of translational studies using swine as a biomedical model.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Animals and ethical statement

Five cross-bred, mixed sex pigs (*Sus scrofa domestica*), 6–18 months old, were used as blood donors. Animals were housed at the Experimental Station of Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale (IZS) of Sardinia (‘Surigheddu’, Sassari, Italy) and animal husbandry, handling, and blood sampling were performed following the Italian Legislative Decree n. 26 dated 4th of March 2014, under the authorization n° 1232/2020-PR.

Animal health was routinely monitored by veterinarians. The absence of several pathogens was evaluated as previously described (Dei Giudici et al., 2020), though quantitative real-time PCR (African swine fever, porcine parvovirus, and porcine circovirus 2), and commercial real-time PCR kits (porcine reproductive and respiratory syndrome virus with LSI VetMAX™ PRRSV EU/NA, and *Mycoplasma hyopneumoniae* VetMAX™-Plus qPCR Master Mix, both Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA), following the manufacturer’s instructions.

2.2. Generation of porcine monocyte-derived macrophages and treatment with diverse polarizing stimuli

Porcine leukocytes were obtained from heparinized blood, as previously described (Franzoni et al., 2020). Then, porcine monocyte-derived macrophages (moM Φ) cultures were generated using Petri dishes and recombinant human M-CSF, as formerly described (Franzoni et al., 2023; Carta et al., 2021; Kapentanovic et al., 2013; Franzoni et al., 2020). In details, leukocytes were incubated at 37 °C 5 % CO₂ in petri dishes in RPMI-1640 supplemented with 10 % fetal bovine serum (FBS), 100 U/mL penicillin, and 100 μ g/mL streptomycin (complete RPMI, cRPMI) supplemented with 50 ng/mL of recombinant human M-CSF (hM-CSF) (Thermo Fisher Scientific). After seven days, culture supernatants (with non-adherent lymphocytes and debris) were removed, adherent cells (moM Φ) were detached by gentle scraping with a pipette, centrifuged at 200 \times g for 8 min, viable cell counts were obtained using a Countess Automated Cell Counter (Thermo Fisher Scientific) (Franzoni et al., 2020).

Cells were seeded in 12-well plates (Greiner CELLSTAR, Merck Life Science), at a density 1 \times 10⁶ live cells per well. After seeding, moM Φ were cultured for 24 h in unsupplemented fresh cRPMI at 37 °C 5 % CO₂. Cells were then left untreated or stimulated for 24 h with diverse molecules. Recombinant porcine IFN- γ (RayBiotech Inc, Norcross, GA, USA) and LPS (lipopolysaccharide from *Escherichia coli* 0111:B4; Merck), both at 100 ng/mL, were used to generate moM(IFN- γ + LPS). ‘M2’ subsets were generated using either recombinant porcine IL-4, IL-10, TGF- β (all R&D Systems, Bio-Techne, Minneapolis, MN, USA), or dexamethasone (Merck), all at 20 ng/mL (Franzoni et al., 2023).

2.3. Expression of key immune genes

Cells were seeded in 12 well plates, left untreated (moM Φ) or treated with diverse polarizing factors: IFN- γ + LPS, IL-4, IL-10, TGF- β , or dexamethasone. 4, 8, and 24 h later, macrophage subsets were harvested to evaluate the gene expression of 16 key immune genes.

Total RNA was extracted with the RNeasy Mini Kit (QIAGEN, Hilden, Germany), and was then eluted in 50 μ L of ultrapure RNase-free water. 250 ng of the purified RNA obtained was used as a template for cDNA synthesis using iScript cDNA (Bio-Rad, Laboratories, Hercules, CA) and then RT-qPCR was employed to determine the expression of key immune genes, as previously described (Franzoni et al., 2023). A list of genes and corresponding primer sets are reported in Table 1.

For all tested genes, five independent experiments using different blood donor pigs were conducted. The relative gene expression levels in each sample were calculated from Cq (quantification cycle) values through the 2^{- $\Delta\Delta$ Cq} method (Franzoni et al., 2020).

2.4. Statistical analysis

Experiments were performed in technical duplicate and repeated with five blood donor pigs. Data were first checked for normality using the Shapiro–Wilk test, and then they were graphically and statistically analyzed with GraphPad Prism 10.01 (GraphPad Software Inc., La Jolla, CA, USA). Differences between macrophage exposed to stimuli and the untreated control (moM Φ) were analyzed through the non-parametric Mann-Whitney test; p value lower than 0.05 were regarded statistically significant (*p < 0.05; ** p < 0.01; *** p < 0.001). Data were presented as box-and-whisker plots, showing median and interquartile range (boxes) and minimum and maximum values (whiskers).

3. Results

Quantitative RT-PCR was employed to investigate expression of selected genes by moM Φ at different timepoints post-stimulation in polarizing stimuli.

Table 1

Genes evaluated and corresponding primer sets.

Gene	Primer sequences	Amplicon length	Accession number
<i>IL1B2</i>	F: 5'-AAATCTCCACCATCTGC-3' R: 5'-CAAGACGATGGGCTCTTCT-3'	156	NM_001302388.2
<i>IL33</i>	F: 5'-GGTAAACCTGAGCCCACAAA-3' R: 5'-TGGCAGTGGGTTTTACATT-3'	97	NM_001285978.1
<i>IL19</i>	F: 5'-TTCCTGCTGCCCATTTGGA-3' R: 5'-GGTGAAACGGGCTCAAACC-3'	81	XM_003130464.3
<i>IL22</i>	F: 5'-TTCAGCAGCCCTACATCAC-3' R: 5'-TAGCAGCGCTCTCTCATCTG-3'	134	XM_021091968.1
<i>IL26</i>	F: 5'-AGCGTGCAAGGAAACAGACT-3' R: 5'-ATCTCTGGGCGATGAAGC-3'	93	XM_005663966.3
<i>CCL17</i>	F: 5'-GGGACGCCATTGTGCTTG-3' R: 5'-TCAGGACTTCTGGGTGACAGG-3'	134	NM_001256147.2
<i>CCL24</i>	F: 5'-CCAGGCAGGGTGATCTTCA-3' R: 5'-TAGTGGAGGCTTTCTCCGC-3'	119	NM_001161434.1
<i>CXCR2</i>	F: 5'-CACTGACCTGCCCTTGATTCT-3' R: 5'-AGCATCACAGGGAGTTTCC-3'	135	XM_021075285.1
<i>MMP9</i>	F: 5'-GGGCTTAGATCACTCAACCG-3' R: 5'-CCGGGGTTCAGGTTTAGGG-3'	136	NM_001038004.1
<i>ARG1</i>	F: 5'-AGCCTGTGTCTTTTCTCCTGA-3' R: 5'-GTCCACGTCTCTCAGGCC-3'	121	NM_214048
<i>NOS2</i>	F: 5'-CGTTATGCCACCAACAATGG-3' R: 5'-AGACCCGGAAGTCGTGCTT-3'	84	NM_001143690.1
<i>MRC1</i>	F: 5'-GCCAGATTCGCAAAGGACAAA-3' R: 5'-CGTGCCTGTCCATGGTTTC-3'	145	NM_001255969.1
<i>FIZZ1</i>	F: 5'-ATCGCAAGGGTTCCTCAGTG-3' R: 5'-AGAGGGATTGAGCTCTAGACGA-3'	87	NM_001103210
<i>VEGFA</i>	F: 5'-CGAGGAAGAAAATCCCTGTG-3' R: 5'-CGTTTAACTCAAGTGCCTCG-3'	132	NM_214084.1
<i>IFNA1</i>	F: 5'-AAGCATCTGCAAGGTTCCCAAT-3' R: 5'-TCCAAAGTCCCTTCTGTGGTC-3'	199	NM_214393.1
<i>IFNB</i>	F: 5'-AGTTGCCTGGGACTCCTCAA-3' R: 5'-CCTCAGGACCTCGAAGTTCAT-3'	60	NM_001003923.1
<i>GAPDH</i>	F: 5'-ATGGTGAAGTTCGGAGTGAA-3' R: 5'-AGTGGAGGTCAATGAAGGGG-3'	264	NM_001206359.1

Fig. 1. Expression of IL-1 family member genes in porcine macrophage subsets. Porcine macrophages were left untreated (moMΦ) or stimulated with diverse polarizing stimuli: IFN- γ + LPS, IL-4, IL-10, TGF- β , dexamethasone. At 4, 8, and 24 h post-stimulation, gene expression levels of two poorly studied IL-1 family members (*IL1B2*, *IL33*) were evaluated with RT-qPCR. At each time point, data were normalized to the values of the untreated control (moMΦ). Data and expressed as $2^{-\Delta\Delta Cq}$, with $\Delta Cq = Cq$ (target gene) - Cq (reference gene), and $\Delta\Delta Cq = \Delta Cq$ (stimulated samples) - ΔCq (moMΦ). Data from five independent experiments are displayed as box-and-whisker plots, showing median and interquartile range (boxes) and minimum and maximum values (whiskers). Values of treated macrophages were compared to moMΦ, using a Mann-Whitney test; *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$.

3.1. Impact of diverse polarization factors on IL-1 and IL10 family member gene expression

In our previous work, we observed interesting peculiarities of porcine moMΦ, such as increased expression of IL1Ra in response to classical activation and increased IL-18 expression in response to IL-4 and IL-10 stimulation (Franzoni et al., 2023). We therefore monitored the induction of two poorly investigated IL-1 family members: IL-1β2 and IL-33 (Shapouri-Moghaddam et al., 2018). We observed that classical activation (IFN-γ + LPS) triggered significant up-regulation of *IL1B2* (8 and 24 h post-stimulation), whereas lower levels of expression were observed in moM(dexamethasone) and moM(IL10) compared to moMΦ at 4 and 24 h post-stimulation. Similarly, stimulation with IFN-γ + LPS induced upregulation of *IL33* (8 and 24 h), whereas exposure to immunosuppressive stimuli downregulated the expression of this IL-1 family member (IL-10 at 8 h, TGF-β at 4,8 and 24 h and dexamethasone at 8 and 24 h) (Fig. 1).

We previously reported that stimulation of porcine moMΦ with IL-10, TGF-β, or glucocorticoids was not associated with enhanced expression and release of IL-10, the M2 hallmark cytokine in other species (Franzoni et al., 2023; Carta et al., 2021). Therefore, we next assessed the expression of three other IL-10 family members: *IL19*, *IL22*,

and *IL26* (Dawson et al., 2020). Stimulation with IFN-γ + LPS induced up-regulation of *IL19* (8 h) and *IL22* (8 and 24 h), but not *IL26*. Exposure to either IL-4, IL-10 or dexamethasone did not alter the expression levels of these interleukins, except for a modest down-regulation of *IL19* at 4 h post-stimulation in moM(dexamethasone) and a downregulation of *IL26* at 24 h post-stimulation in moM(IL-4) compared to moMΦ. Interestingly, stimulation with TGF-β triggered up-regulation of *IL19* (24 h), *IL22* (24 h), *IL26* (4, 8, and 24 h) (Fig. 2).

3.2. Impact of diverse polarization factors on chemokine gene expression

Macrophage polarization is associated with marked changes in chemokine expression profiles (Mantovani et al., 2004). In humans, classical activation of macrophages increased expression of several proinflammatory chemokines, whereas exposure to IL-4 selectively induced *CCL24* and *CCL17* expression (Mantovani et al., 2004). In this study, we therefore monitored expression of these chemokines in porcine moMΦ. RT-qPCR data showed that IFN-γ + LPS stimulation did not modulate the expression of these chemokines, whereas exposure to IL-4 increased expression of *CCL17* (4, 8 and 24 h) and *CCL24* (8 and 24 h). Treatment with IL-10, TGF-β and dexamethasone decreased *CCL17* expression, with statistical significance for all at 24 h

Fig. 2. Expression of IL-10 family member genes in porcine macrophage subsets. Porcine macrophages were left untreated (moMΦ) or stimulated with diverse polarizing stimuli: IFN-γ + LPS, IL-4, IL-10, TGF-β, dexamethasone. At 4, 8, and 24 h post-stimulation, gene expression levels of three poorly investigated IL-10 family members (*IL19*, *IL22*, *IL26*) were evaluated with RT-qPCR. At each time point, data were normalized to the values of the untreated control (moMΦ). Data and expressed as $2^{-\Delta\Delta Cq}$, with $\Delta Cq = Cq$ (target gene) – Cq (reference gene), and $\Delta\Delta Cq = \Delta Cq$ (stimulated samples) – ΔCq (moMΦ). Data from five independent experiments are displayed as box-and-whisker plots, showing median and interquartile range (boxes) and minimum and maximum values (whiskers). Values of treated macrophages were compared to moMΦ, using a Mann-Whitney test; *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$.

post-stimulation. Both TGF- β and dexamethasone slightly up-regulated *CCL24* levels (TGF- β at 24 h and dexamethasone at 8 h), but with lower intensity compared to the IL-4 stimulus (Fig. 3). Exposure to IL-4 increased expression of the chemokine receptor *CXCR2* at all timepoints tested. No differences were observed between the other macrophage subsets and the untreated control, except for a reduced expression in moM(IL-10) at 24 h (Fig. 3).

3.3. Impact of diverse polarization factors on type I interferon gene expression

In many species, including pigs and humans, macrophages stimulated with IFN- γ + LPS are distinguished by an antimicrobial phenotype, whereas macrophage exposure to anti-inflammatory cytokines is characterized by an immunosuppressive phenotype (Mosser, 2003; Carta et al., 2021; Franzoni et al., 2023). We next investigated the impact of macrophage polarization on the expression of two genes crucial in defense to viruses: *IFNA1*, and *IFNB*. We observed no significant modulation of *IFNA1* in response to stimulation with the five tested stimuli, except a slight transient down-regulation in moM(IL-4) at 4 h (Fig. 4). As expected, exposure to IFN- γ + LPS increased expression of *IFNB*, with

statistical significance at 4 h. Exposure to the other three M2-related stimuli instead down-regulated expression of *IFNB*: IL-4 (24 h), IL-10 (24 h), and dexamethasone (4 and 8 h) (Fig. 4).

3.4. Impact of diverse polarization factors on genes encoding M2-related factors

We next monitored the expression of selected M2-related genes, such as *MRC1* and found in inflammatory zone-1 (*FIZZ1*) (Martinez and Gordon, 2014). The *MRC1*-encoded mannose receptor C-type I is a pattern recognition receptor and stimulation with IL-4 enhances its expression in both human and murine macrophages (Martinez and Gordon, 2014). In pigs, we observed that stimulation with IFN- γ + LPS down-regulated *MRC1* expression (24 h). None of the M2-related stimuli triggered decreased expression of *MRC1*, except for TGF- β (24 h), whereas the other two M2-related stimuli (IL-4, dexamethasone) increased *MRC1* expression: IL-4 at 4 h and dexamethasone at 8 and 24 h. IL-10 stimulation did not significantly affect *MRC1* expression at any of the tested time points (Fig. 4). In mice, *FIZZ1* expression was enhanced in macrophages stimulated with IL-4 (Martinez and Gordon, 2014). Surprisingly, in pigs we found that IL-4 decreased expression of

Fig. 3. Expression of selected chemokine genes in porcine macrophage subsets. Porcine macrophages were left untreated (moM Φ) or stimulated with diverse polarizing stimuli: IFN- γ + LPS, IL-4, IL-10, TGF- β , dexamethasone. At 4, 8, and 24 h post-stimulation, gene expression levels of CCL17, CCL24, and the chemokine receptors CXCR2 were evaluated with RT-qPCR. At each time point, data were normalized to the values of the untreated control (moM Φ). Data and expressed as $2^{-\Delta\Delta Cq}$, with $\Delta Cq = Cq$ (target gene) - Cq (reference gene), and $\Delta\Delta Cq = \Delta Cq$ (stimulated samples) - ΔCq (moM Φ). Data from five independent experiments are displayed as box-and-whisker plots, showing median and interquartile range (boxes) and minimum and maximum values (whiskers). Values of treated macrophages were compared to moM Φ , using an unpaired T test or a Mann-Whitney test; *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$.

Fig. 4. Expression of type I interferon genes in porcine macrophage subsets. Porcine macrophages were left untreated (moMΦ) or stimulated with diverse polarizing stimuli: IFN- γ + LPS, IL-4, IL-10, TGF- β , dexamethasone. At 4, 8, and 24 h post-stimulation, gene expression levels of two type I interferons (*IFNA1*, *IFNB*) were evaluated with RT-qPCR. At each time point, data were normalized to the values of the untreated control (moMΦ). Data and expressed as $2^{-\Delta\Delta Cq}$, with $\Delta Cq = Cq$ (target gene) – Cq (reference gene), and $\Delta\Delta Cq = \Delta Cq$ (stimulated samples) – ΔCq (moMΦ). Data from five independent experiments are displayed as box-and-whisker plots, showing median and interquartile range (boxes) and minimum and maximum values (whiskers). Values of treated macrophages were compared to moMΦ, using an unpaired T test or a Mann-Whitney test; *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$.

FIZZ1 at 4 and 24 h post-stimulation. In addition, we observed lower *FIZZ1* expression in moM(IFN- γ + LPS) and moM(IL-10) compared to moMΦ at 24 h (Fig. 5).

There is contrasting information on the role of other molecules in macrophage polarization, such as vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF)-A and matrix metalloproteinase (MMP)-9. The latter is an endopeptidase with a pivotal role in degradation of extracellular matrix and tissue remodeling (Yabluchanskiy et al., 2013). We observed that stimulation with IFN- γ + LPS did not modulate *MMP9* expression. None of the M2-related stimuli triggered increased the expression of this metalloprotease, except for a modest and transient raise in moM(TGF- β) (4 h). Interestingly, three M2-related stimuli (IL-4, IL-10, dexamethasone) decreased *MMP9* expression (dexamethasone at 4 h, IL-4 at 8 h, and IL-10 at 24 h) (Fig. 5). VEGF-A is a member of the platelet derived growth factor super-family (Dawson et al., 2020), and has a pro-angiogenic effects (Chung and Ferrara, 2011). It is frequently associated with tumor-associated macrophages (TAM) (Rószler, 2015). We observed that *VEGFA* expression was enhanced in macrophages stimulated with IFN- γ + LPS compared to untreated moMΦ, with statistical significance at 4 and 8 h post-stimulation. We observed decreased *VEGFA* expression in three other macrophage subsets: moM (IL4) (at 4, 8, and 24 h), moM(IL-10) (24 h), moM(dexamethasone) (8 and 24 h) (Fig. 5).

3.5. Impact of diverse polarization factors on genes encoding enzymes involved in arginine metabolism

Finally, we investigated the impact of diverse polarizing factors on expression of genes encoding two key enzymes involved in arginine metabolism: arginase 1 (*ARG1*) and nitric oxide synthase 2 (*NOS2*), the latter encoding for the enzyme inducible nitric oxide synthase (iNOS). In humans and mice, M(IFN- γ + LPS) express iNOS, which generates nitric oxide (NO) from arginine, whereas expression of the arginase enzyme is

a hallmark of M2 polarization (Rath et al., 2014). As expected, stimulation with IL-4 increased expression of *ARG1* at all tested time points. Stimulation with IL-10 did not significantly affect *ARG1* expression, whereas stimulation with either TGF- β or dexamethasone slightly increased expression (TGF- β at 8 and 24 h, and dexamethasone at 8 h). Surprisingly, we observed that IFN- γ + LPS stimulation increased *ARG1* expression at 8 and 24 h, although in a less marked way compared to IL-4. Expression of *NOS2* was selectively upregulated in response to IFN- γ + LPS, with increased expression observed at all time-points. All the other stimuli decreased *NOS2* expression: IL-4 (4, 8 and 24 h), IL-10 (24 h), TGF- β (24 h), dexamethasone (4 and 24 h) (Fig. 6).

4. Discussion

Pigs are attracting increased interest as a close-to-human biomedical model and their immune system present several analogies with humans (Mair et al., 2014). However, porcine macrophage polarization has not been completely characterized. In our recent studies, we assessed porcine macrophage polarization and identified interesting singularities (Carta et al., 2021; Franzoni et al., 2023). Therefore in this study, we aimed to further understand porcine macrophage polarization by screening expression of sixteen selected genes in porcine moMΦ stimulated with IFN- γ + LPS (classical activation), or by different 'M2' polarizing stimuli: IL-4, IL-10, TGF- β , and dexamethasone.

We first investigated the expression of selected interleukins. Since our previous work highlighted an unexpected increase in expression of IL1Ra in porcine moMΦ responding to classical activation and increased IL-18 expression in response to IL-4 and IL-10 stimulation (Franzoni et al., 2023), we investigated the gene expression of other two IL-1 family members in porcine moMΦ subsets: *IL33* and *IL1 β 2*. In humans and mice, IL-33 is associated with the production of Th2-associated cytokines, increased serum immunoglobulin levels, eosinophil recruitment, as well as a 'M2-like' macrophage polarization (Schmitz et al.,

Fig. 5. Expression of genes encoding M2-related factors in diverse porcine macrophage subsets. Porcine macrophages were left untreated (moM Φ) or stimulated with diverse polarizing stimuli: IFN- γ + LPS, IL-4, IL-10, TGF- β , dexamethasone. At 4, 8, and 24 h post-stimulation, gene expression levels of five M2-like factors (FIZZ1, MRC1, MMP9, VEGFA) were evaluated with RT-qPCR. At each time point, data were normalized to the values of the untreated control (moM Φ). Data and expressed as $2^{-\Delta\Delta Cq}$, with $\Delta Cq = Cq$ (target gene) – Cq (reference gene), and $\Delta\Delta Cq = \Delta Cq$ (stimulated samples) – ΔCq (moM Φ). Data from five independent experiments are displayed as box-and-whisker plots, showing median and interquartile range (boxes) and minimum and maximum values (whiskers). Values of treated macrophages were compared to moM Φ , using an unpaired T test or a Mann-Whitney test; *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$.

2005; Garlanda et al., 2013). We observed *IL33* upregulation in macrophages exposed to IFN- γ + LPS, and downregulation in response to immunosuppressive cytokines (IL-10 or TGF- β) or dexamethasone. This trend is similar to what we previously observed for IL-1Ra (Franzoni et al., 2023) and we hypothesize that this may be a regulatory mechanism. Macrophages stimulated with IFN- γ + LPS are associated with a proinflammatory phenotype, thus the release of IL-1Ra and IL-33 can counteract the development of pathogenic inflammatory responses. In pigs, an IL-1 β paralog was recently described (IL-1 β 2), whose functions have not been fully elucidated (Dawson et al., 2020; Liu et al., 2018). In this study, we observed that classical but not alternative activation triggered *IL1B2* expression, in a comparable manner to that of IL-1 β ; the role of this IL-1 β paralog in defense against intracellular pathogens or tumors deserves further investigation.

We and others described that stimulation of porcine macrophages with IL-4, IL-10, TGF- β , or glucocorticoids was not associated with enhanced expression and release of IL-10 (Franzoni et al., 2017; Sautter

et al., 2018; Carta et al., 2021; Franzoni et al., 2023), which is contrary to what was observed in other species (Gordon, 2003; Gordon and Martinez, 2010). We therefore investigated the expression of three other IL-10 family member genes, *IL19*, *IL22*, and *IL26*, by porcine moM Φ subsets (Dawson et al., 2020). IL-19 promotes Th2 responses by inducing expression/release of Th2 cytokines (Gallagher, 2010; Gallagher et al., 2000), and it plays a role in the pathogenesis of psoriasis (Gallagher, 2010; Azuma et al., 2011) and asthma (Weng et al., 2019). In accordance with human monocyte data (Gallagher et al., 2000; Azuma et al., 2011), we observed that stimulation with IFN- γ + LPS induced upregulation of *IL19* in porcine macrophages, which was likely due to LPS. Exposure to IL-4 or IL-10 did not affect expression of *IL19*, and only a modest down-regulation was observed in moM(dexamethasone) at 4 h post-stimulation. Interestingly, stimulation with TGF- β triggered a sustained *IL19* up-regulation at 24 h post-stimulation. A similar pattern was observed for *IL22*, which was enhanced by stimulation with IFN- γ + LPS or TGF- β . IL-22 plays a critical role in wound healing, promotes

Fig. 6. Expression of genes encoding key enzymes of arginine metabolism in diverse porcine macrophage subsets. Porcine macrophages were left untreated (moMΦ) or stimulated with diverse polarizing stimuli: IFN- γ + LPS, IL-4, IL-10, TGF- β , dexamethasone. At 4, 8, and 24 h post-stimulation, gene expression levels of five M2-like factors (*ARG1*, and *NOS2*) were evaluated with RT-qPCR. At each time point, data were normalized to the values of the untreated control (moMΦ). Data and expressed as $2^{-\Delta\Delta Cq}$, with $\Delta Cq = Cq$ (target gene) – Cq (reference gene), and $\Delta\Delta Cq = \Delta Cq$ (stimulated samples) – ΔCq (moMΦ). Data from five independent experiments are displayed as box-and-whisker plots, showing median and interquartile range (boxes) and minimum and maximum values (whiskers). Values of treated macrophages were compared to moMΦ, using an unpaired T test or a Mann-Whitney test; *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$.

M2-polarization in mice, but high levels were also correlated with inflammatory tissue pathology (Dudakov et al., 2015; Luo et al., 2016; Zaharie et al., 2022). Future studies should better depict the role of IL-22 in tumor progression and its expression by porcine tumor associated macrophages (TAMs). In humans and mice, IL-26 promoted macrophage polarization toward an M1 phenotype, with induction of pro-inflammatory cytokines and iNOS (Lin et al., 2020). In pigs, we observed no modulation of *IL26* expression in response to stimulation with IFN- γ + LPS. A slight enhancement was observed in response to stimulation with TGF- β . Overall, these data further highlight macrophage heterogeneity in pigs and interesting differences in IL-10 family members even between porcine macrophage subsets generated with similar stimuli (IL-10, TGF- β , and dexamethasone).

We next investigated the expression of selected chemokines. In humans and mice, M1 macrophages are characterized by increased expression/release of pro-inflammatory chemokines, whereas M2-inducing signals trigger expression of a specific subset of chemokines, such as CCL17 and CCL24 (Mantovani et al., 2004). CCL17 and CCL24 promote the recruitment of eosinophils, basophils, and Th2 cells, and are selectively induced by IL-4 (Mantovani et al., 2004). We observed that *CCL17* was up-regulated by IL-4 but not by 'M2c-related' stimuli (IL-10, TGF- β , dexamethasone), which is in agreement to what described in humans and rodents. Expression of *CCL24* was upregulated by IL-4, and to a lesser extent by TGF- β and dexamethasone. Only IL-4 stimulation markedly increased expression of the *CXCR2* chemokine receptor gene. These data suggest that *CCL17* and *CXCR2* can define porcine M(IL-4) polarization.

We investigated the impact of macrophage polarization on the expression of two type I interferon encoding genes (*IFNA1*, *IFNB*) since they play a pivotal role in the innate immune response to viral infections (Parkin and Cohen, 2001). *IFNA1* expression was not modulated by the tested stimuli, except for a weak transient down-regulation in moM (IL-4). As expected, exposure to IFN- γ + LPS increased expression of

IFNB, whereas its levels were decreased by IL-4, IL-10, dexamethasone. These data are in line with that described in other species, where M1 macrophages are a key component of the innate immune response to viruses (Mantovani et al., 2004; Yu et al., 2022).

We monitored gene expression of selected M2-related factors over time. *MRC1*, also known as CD206, is a mannose receptor whose expression in human and murine macrophages is enhanced by IL-4 stimulation (Martinez and Gordon, 2014; (Gordon and Martinez, 2010). Previous studies in pigs showed instead no modulation of *MRC1* in response to stimulation with diverse stimuli, such as IL-4, IFN- γ + LPS (Singleton et al., 2016), IFN- γ or IFN- β (Sautter et al., 2018). We observed that IFN- γ + LPS stimulation down-regulated *MRC1* expression, whereas two M2-related stimuli (IL-4 and dexamethasone) increased expression. However, *MRC1* expression levels increased only transiently following IL-4 stimulation (4 h) and this was not appreciable at later timepoints (8 and 24 h). *FIZZ1*, also known as Relm α or Retnla, is regarded as a hallmark of M2 polarization in mice (Martinez and Gordon, 2014). Surprisingly, we observed that IL-4 stimulation of porcine moMΦ decreased *FIZZ1* expression at 4 and 24 h post-stimulation. We also observed that *FIZZ1* was downregulated in both moM(IFN- γ + LPS) and moM(IL-10) at 24 h, thus we can assume that it cannot be used to define M2 subsets in pigs.

VEGF-A is an enzyme involved in physiological development and maintenance of the vascular and lymphatic systems (Chung and Ferrara, 2011). VEGF-A has proangiogenic impacts and can promote tumor development and metastasis by increasing TAM invasion and M2 polarization (Röszer, 2015; Zhang and Sioud, 2023; Mishra et al., 2022). Some studies found that VEGF-A was produced in response to M1-stimuli (Spiller et al., 2014), whereas others described that high *VEGFA* expression was associated with M2-like polarization (Mishra et al., 2022; Wheeler et al., 2018). We observed that *VEGFA* was selectively upregulated by stimulation with IFN- γ + LPS and reduced in response to stimulation with three M2-related stimuli (IL-4, IL-10, and

dexamethasone), suggesting that *VEGFA* expression is associated with a porcine M1-phenotype. Human 'M2d' macrophages are characterized by VEGF expression (Griener et al., 2009). Future studies in pigs should explore the impact of 'M2d-related' stimuli, such as IL-6 or TLR-agonists in association with adenosine A2A receptor agonists (Zhang and Sioud, 2023), on macrophage phenotype and functionalities.

MMP9 is an enzyme involved in tissue remodeling (Yabluchanskiy et al., 2013). Studies have suggested that MMP9 expression is enhanced in M1 macrophages (Spiller et al., 2014), whereas others reported release by M2-like macrophages and a role in promoting tumor progression (Wheeler et al., 2018; Tian et al., 2022). MMP9 can be released by TAMs, increasing degradation of the extracellular matrix, and thus facilitating metastasis (Zhang and Sioud, 2023). We observed that stimulation with neither IFN- γ + LPS nor M2-related stimuli increased *MMP9* expression, except for a modest and transient increase in moM(TGF- β). In addition, three M2-related stimuli (IL-4, IL-10, and dexamethasone) transiently decreased *MMP9* expression. Our data suggests that *MMP9* expression in porcine macrophages is not related to an immunosuppressive phenotype, and it is also not associated with either M1 or M(IL4) subsets. Further studies should

investigate *MMP9* expression by porcine TAM.

Finally, we assessed the effect of diverse polarizing factors on genes encoding two key enzymes of the arginine metabolism pathway, which has a determining role for the M1/M2 dichotomy: *NOS2* and *ARG1*. In humans and mice, M1 macrophages express the *NOS2* encoded iNOS, which generates nitric oxide (NO) from arginine. In agreement, we observed that *NOS2* expression was selectively upregulated in response to IFN- γ + LPS, whereas all the other tested stimuli (IL-4, IL-10, TGF- β , dexamethasone) decreased its expression. *ARG1* induction is regarded as a hallmark of M(IL-4) in many species (Rath et al., 2014), including pigs (Sautter et al., 2018; Carta et al., 2021; Álvarez et al., 2023). As expected, stimulation with IL-4 increased *ARG1* expression in porcine moM Φ . In rodents, both IL-10 and TGF- β increased arginase activity in macrophages (Boutard et al., 1995; Munder et al., 1998), whereas this was not observed in humans (Shapouri-Moghaddam et al., 2018). We observed that IL-10 stimulation did not affect *ARG1* expression, in agreement with our previous work (Carta et al., 2021). We observed that stimulation with TGF- β increased *ARG1* expression, although in a weaker manner compared to IL-4, similar to what we previously described (Carta et al., 2021). A weak enhancement of *ARG1* expression

Table 2

Summary of the impact of polarizing stimuli on porcine monocyte-derived macrophage gene expression.

Gene	Impact of M1/M2 polarizing stimuli	Similarities with human/murine macrophages
<i>IL1B2</i>	IFN- γ + LPS \rightarrow upregulation (8, 24 h) IL10 \rightarrow downregulation (24 h) dexamethasone \rightarrow downregulation (4 h)	Unknown
<i>IL33</i>	IFN- γ + LPS \rightarrow upregulation (8, 24 h) IL10 \rightarrow downregulation (8, 24 h) dexamethasone \rightarrow downregulation (4, 8, 24 h)	No \rightarrow IL-33 expression associated with 'M2-like' macrophage polarization in humans and mice (Garlanda et al., 2013).
<i>IL19</i>	IFN- γ + LPS \rightarrow upregulation (8 h); TGF- β \rightarrow upregulation (24 h); dexamethasone \rightarrow downregulation (4 h).	Similar \rightarrow <i>IL19</i> expression in human monocytes is enhanced by stimulation with LPS, but not IFN- γ , IL-4 or IL-10 (Gallagher et al., 2000; Azuma et al., 2011).
<i>IL22</i>	IFN- γ + LPS \rightarrow upregulation (8, 24 h) TGF- β \rightarrow upregulation (24 h)	No \rightarrow IL-22 expression associated with 'M2-like' macrophage polarization in humans and mice (Luo et al., 2016; Zaharie et al., 2022).
<i>IL26</i>	TGF- β \rightarrow upregulation (4, 8, 24 h) IL-4, IL-10 \rightarrow downregulation (24 h)	No \rightarrow IL-26 associated with M1 macrophage polarization in humans and mice (Lin et al., 2020).
<i>CCL17</i>	IL-4 \rightarrow upregulation (4, 8, 24 h) IL10 \rightarrow downregulation (8, 24 h) TGF- β , dexamethasone \rightarrow downregulation (24 h)	Yes \rightarrow CCL17 associated with M2 polarization in humans and mice, selectively induced by IL-4 (Mantovani et al., 2004).
<i>CCL24</i>	IL-4 \rightarrow upregulation (8, 24 h) TGF- β \rightarrow modest upregulation (24 h) dexamethasone \rightarrow modest upregulation (8 h)	Mostly \rightarrow CCL24 associated with M2 polarization in humans and mice, selectively induced by IL-4 (Mantovani et al., 2004).
<i>CXCR2</i>	IL-4 \rightarrow upregulation (4, 8, 24 h) IL10 \rightarrow downregulation (24 h)	Yes \rightarrow CXCR2 associated with M2 polarization in humans and mice (Mantovani et al., 2004).
<i>IFNA1</i>	IL-4 \rightarrow downregulation (4 h)	Yes \rightarrow Type I IFNs associated with M1 polarization in humans and mice (Mantovani et al., 2004).
<i>IFNB</i>	IFN- γ + LPS \rightarrow upregulation (4 h) IL-4, IL10 \rightarrow downregulation (24 h) dexamethasone \rightarrow downregulation (4, 8 h)	Yes \rightarrow Type I IFNs associated with M1 polarization in humans and mice (Mantovani et al., 2004).
<i>MRC1</i>	IL-4 \rightarrow upregulation (4 h) dexamethasone \rightarrow upregulation (8, 24 h) IFN- γ + LPS \rightarrow downregulation (24 h) TGF- β \rightarrow downregulation (24 h)	Yes \rightarrow Stimulation with IL-4 enhances <i>MRC1</i> expression in both human and murine macrophages (Martinez and Gordon, 2014; Gordon and Martinez, 2010). Stimulation with dexamethasone promotes CD206 expression in human macrophages (Diez-Tercero et al., 2022).
<i>FIZZ1</i>	IFN- γ + LPS \rightarrow downregulation (24 h) IL-4 \rightarrow downregulation (4, 24 h) IL-10 \rightarrow downregulation (24 h)	No \rightarrow FIZZ1 is regarded as a hallmark of M2 polarization in mice; IL-4 enhances <i>FIZZ1</i> expression in murine macrophages (Martinez and Gordon, 2014).
<i>MMP9</i>	TGF- β \rightarrow modest upregulation (4 h) IL-4 \rightarrow downregulation (8 h) IL10 \rightarrow downregulation (24 h) dexamethasone \rightarrow modest downregulation (4 h)	Contrasting results in humans: some authors suggested that <i>MMP9</i> expression is enhanced in human M1 macrophages (Spiller et al., 2014), whereas others reported release by human M2-like macrophages (Wheeler et al., 2018).
<i>VEGFA</i>	IFN- γ + LPS \rightarrow upregulation (4, 8 h) IL-4 \rightarrow downregulation (4, 8, 24 h) IL-10 \rightarrow downregulation (24 h) dexamethasone \rightarrow downregulation (8, 24 h)	Contrasting results in humans: some studies found that VEGF-A was induced in human M1 macrophages (Spiller et al., 2014), whereas others reported high <i>VEGFA</i> expression in response to human M2-like polarization (Mishra et al., 2022; Wheeler et al., 2018).
<i>ARG1</i>	IFN- γ + LPS \rightarrow upregulation (8, 24 h) IL-4 \rightarrow strong upregulation (4, 8, 24 h) TGF- β \rightarrow upregulation (8, 24 h) dexamethasone \rightarrow upregulation (8 h)	Yes \rightarrow <i>ARG1</i> expression is a hallmark of M(IL-4) polarization in humans, mice and other species (Rath et al., 2014)
<i>NOS2</i>	IFN- γ + LPS \rightarrow upregulation (4, 8, 24 h) IL-4 \rightarrow downregulation (4, 8, 24 h) IL-10, TGF- β \rightarrow downregulation (24 h) dexamethasone \rightarrow downregulation (4, 24 h)	Yes \rightarrow humans and murine M1 macrophages express the <i>NOS2</i> encoded iNOS (Rath et al., 2014)

was also observed in moM(dexamethasone). Surprisingly, we observed that stimulation of IFN- γ + LPS slightly increased *ARG1* expression at 8 and 24 h post-stimulation. Menzies and colleagues (2010) reported that LPS stimulated arginase activity in murine bone marrow-derived macrophages (Menzies et al., 2010). Thus, we speculate that the modest transient expression observed in this study was due to stimulation with LPS. Overall, these data suggest that expression of *NOS2* and *ARG1* can be useful markers to define macrophage polarization in pigs, although scientists should consider that diverse immunosuppressive stimuli, such as IL-10, TGF- β , dexamethasone can differently modulate *ARG1* expression.

Table 2 summarizes the findings from this study, highlighting the key similarities and differences between polarized porcine macrophage subsets and their human and murine counterparts.

5. Conclusions

In this work, we observed that macrophage polarization in pigs resembles that of human and murine macrophages. However, some porcine-specific peculiarities were described, such as increased expression of *IL33* in response to stimulation with IFN- γ + LPS and not M2-related stimuli. None of the tested M2-related stimuli upregulated the expression of *FIZZ1*, *MMP9* or *VEGFA*. This study highlighted the heterogeneity of porcine macrophages, showing that even similar anti-inflammatory stimuli (IL-10, TGF- β , dexamethasone) gave rise to cells with diverse phenotypes. Data generated by this work should aid researchers to better interpret both *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies using swine as a close-to-human biomedical model.

Ethics statement

The present study was conducted according to the guidelines of the Declaration of Helsinki and approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee of the Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale della Sardegna. Animal husbandry and procedures (blood sampling) were authorized by the Italian Ministry of Health, with the authorization n° 1232/2020-PR.

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CRediT authorship contribution statement

Simon Graham: Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Silvia Dei Giudici:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Susanna Zinellu:** Methodology, Investigation. **Nicolò Columbano:** Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **Giulia Franzoni:** Writing – original draft, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Floriana Fruscione:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Elisabetta Razuoli:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Filippo Dell'Anno:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Lorena Mura:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Chiara De Ciucis:** Methodology, Investigation.

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

The authors declare no use of AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors have nothing to declare.

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